

Bullying Others as an Outcome of Abused Childhood

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Abstract: *The paper attempts to investigate and dwell upon the definitions and the nature of Bullying present in the contemporary world which has a telling impact on the peer group. How a childhood can peter off into the vanity of delinquency and can lead to a harmful influence on the peer group of the bully and the immediate societal context. The paper highlights the psychological and neurotic factors which explain such a violently deviant behavior in childhood and younger years. The paper argues that it's the factor of Force Majore which vitiates a childhood's growth trajectory and leads to deviancy.*

Keywords: Bully, Bullying, Force Majore, Abuse.

Methodology

The paper utilizes a descriptive and explanatory method of weaving a rationale for the theme and the presented research. The author utilizes a litany of secondary source material of the order of Books, papers, web sources and journal studies in order to develop and argue for the theme chosen.

Introduction

“Bully, Get away from me?” These are the words that would normally and ordinarily emanate from the mouth of a victim of the malady of bullying. A Bully might be an elder brother, senior at school or College or even a colleague or teacher at a work place. This amounts to an observation upon the theme of human behavior where-in, the force on behavior of a bully is part of a well brought out study. Dominance and Force happens to be part of an intrinsic part of human nature which reflects itself through the behavior of humans.

The terms which have been discussed and mentioned in the abstract can be elaborated upon here. A *bully* is a person who may be a senior, a colleague or a boss at work which psychologically molests a person. *Force Majore* is an act of forceful behavior which can be termed as being male factory and vile as it has a demeaning and belittling impact on the victim or the personage who is exposed to the excessively aggressive behavior leading to

dehumanization of the person who is bullied which might have psychological and physical and societal impact on the victim leading to personal suffering. Abuse is another term which has been bandied about in the narrative of the paper. It refers to a deleterious behavior or heinous act on the part of a bully or an abuser who perpetrates an act which has a belittling impact and sufferance of ignominy and humiliation in the context of a human relationship or a societal context.

There has to be a reason and a well hewn rationale why a specific individual behaves in a peculiarly forceful and harsh demeanor. The rationale generally happens to be a psychotic condition being reached by the individual as he or she has been exposed to threatening abusive behavior and treatment when the bully was growing up as a toddler.

How to Define Bullying

Discussions:

A standard and quintessential definition of Bullying can be advanced here safely as part of the narrative of the paper. The definition goes by, “Bullying is a distinctive pattern of repeatedly and deliberately harming and humiliating others, specifically those who are smaller, weaker, younger or in any way more vulnerable than the bully. The deliberate targeting of those of lesser power is what distinguishes bullying from garden-variety aggression.”

The same web portal informs us that, “Bullying can involve verbal attacks (name-calling and making fun of others) as well as physical ones, threats of harm, other forms of intimidation, and deliberate exclusion from activities. Studies indicate that bullying peaks around ages 11 to 13 and decreases as children grow older. Overt physical aggression such as kicking, hitting, and shoving is most common among younger children; relational aggression—damaging or manipulating the relationships of others, such as spreading rumours, and social exclusion—is more common as children mature.”¹ Force Majore has been the order of the day as far as the tenet and the behaviour of bullying is concerned. It’s a reflection and manifestation of aggression which is best exemplified by a striving to dominate, hurt or humiliate the weaker, smaller and a vulnerable lot or an individual personage.

It can be argued that, “Most bullying occurs in and around school and on playgrounds, although the internet lends itself to particularly distressing forms of bullying. Approximately 20 percent of students report being bullied at school, according to the National Center

¹ Ibid
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for Education Statistics. Boys and girls are equally likely to be bullied.”² It’s in the early schooling years of a person’s period that bullying occurs and is found rampant in a well manifested manner. As people grow older and attain years in life, it has been observed that bullying becomes a lesser encountered behaviour.

A verifiable publication in the realm of psychology informs us that, “Bullying behavior is a serious problem among school-age children and adolescents; it has short- and long-term effects on the individual who is bullied, the individual who bullies, the individual who is bullied and bullies others, and the bystander present during the bullying event. One needs to be aware of the harmful and deleterious influence of the consequences of bullying behaviour for children and youth.”³ When a victim in nascent age gets bullied then he or she faces a social prestige issue as he or she is humiliated before the community’s eye and may turn the victim into a cynosure of all eyes. Also, the victim may recede into depression and may face stultifying growth along with developing a violent confrontationist streak which can harm both the bully and the bullied, both.

The Historicity attached to Bullying Behaviour: Discussions: The Review of Literature

One may delve inside amidst a bullying historicity that is present in the available literature in the stream of psychology. This process of delving inside the concerned theme can be attained through a brief and quick review of literature. Burke writes that, “Bullying behaviour was first characterized in the scientific literature as part of the childhood experience more than 100 years ago in “Teasing and Bullying,” published in the *Pedagogical Seminary*”.⁴ Koo pens that, “The author described bullying behavior, attempted to delineate causes and cures for the tormenting of others, and called for additional research.”⁵ Olweus writes that, “Nearly a century later, Dan Olweus, a Swedish research professor of psychology in Norway, conducted an intensive study on bullying.”⁶ The author further stresses that, “The efforts of Olweus brought awareness to the issue and motivated other professionals to conduct their own research, thereby expanding and contributing to knowledge of bullying behaviour. Since Olweus’s early work, research on bullying has steadily increased.”⁷ Thus, the basic and fundamental approaches and definitions

² Ibid 1

³ “Eradicating Bullying through Science and Policy,” National Academics Press, 2016

⁴ Urk FL. Teasing and bullying. *The Pedagogical Seminary*. 1897;4(3):336–371

⁵ Koo H. A time line of the evolution of school bullying in differing social contexts. *Asia Pacific Education Review*. 2007;8(1):107–116

⁶ Olweus D. *Aggression in the Schools: Bullies and Whipping Boys*. Washington, DC: Hemisphere; 1978

⁷ Ibid

of Bullying have a great convergence and consonance in meaning and spirit with inflicting torment being the order of the day for the sake of the academics and research.

Bob Sornson pens that, “Written by teachers with a focus on empowering ⁸kids to stand up for others, *The Juice Box Bully* is about a new student named Pete, who is using bullying behaviour on the first day of school. However, the other students decide to call it out and instead of being bystanders, intervene with kindness and assertiveness.”⁹ Barbara Coloroso writes that, “A guide for parents and educators offers advice on recognizing bullying behavior while making suggestions on how to appropriately discipline bullies, protect children, and formulate constructive school and community practices.” Explores the issues surrounding cyberbullying–bullying through the Internet–by placing opinions from a wide range of sources in a pro/con format.

Hovens writes that, “Childhood trauma has been linked to the development of anxiety and depression in later life.”¹⁰ Lindert writes that “A history of abuse may be more identifiable by adulthood as emotional and behavioral patterns have evolved by this period. As of this, various disorders are likely to arise among childhood abuse victims.”¹¹ “More specifically, the connection between depression, anxiety and childhood trauma could be related to the individual's neurological response system. Repeated childhood exposure to severe stressors causes excessive transmission of stress hormones in the body, as a way of responding to the event(s) that are happening around them.”¹² Regular exposure to toxic conditions in childhood can distort the biological makeup of the body's Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal (HPA) axis. This neurological system sends signals to the brain to alert the body of dangerous circumstances. Butler and Maack write that, “When the HPA axis is over activated the secretion of stress hormones creates a surplus and the body remains alert in preparation to react to perceived harmful situations through the fight-flight-freeze system. If a state of readiness through this system occurs frequently, it permits over activation throughout childhood and later

⁸ Barbara Coloroso, “The Bullies, The Bully and the Bystander,” New Viking: New York, 2008

⁹ Bob Sornson, “Juice Box Bully,” Viking Books, 2012

¹⁰ J.G.F.M. Hovens, J.E. Wiersma, E.J. Giltay, P. van Oppen, P. Spinhoven, B.W.J.H Penninx, F.G. Zitman Childhood life events and childhood trauma in adult patients with depressive, anxiety and comorbid disorders vs. Controls *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 122 (1) (2010), pp. 66-74

¹¹ J. Lindert, O.S. von Ehrenstein, R. Grashow, G. Gal, E. Braehler, M.G. Weisskopf Sexual and physical abuse in childhood is associated with depression and anxiety over the life course: systematic review and meta-analysis *International Journal of Public Health*, 59 (2) (2014), pp. 359-372

¹² C. Heim, D.J. Newport, T. Mletzko, A.H. Miller, C.B. Nemeroff The link between childhood trauma and depression: Insights from HPA axis studies in humans *Psycho neuroendocrinology*, 33 (6) (2008), pp. 693-710

promotes the risk of depressive and anxiety disorders due to heightened cortisol levels following traumatic episodes.”¹³ Thus psychosomatic maladies seemingly manifest themselves in the lives of bullies and children who have faced abuse in their toddlerhood and even substance abuse in an adolescent age is directly linked to the drugs usage and alcoholism which pervades the unstable and besieged life styles of some the children who have faced child abuse. Bellville, Guay and Marchand write that, “Overcoming trauma can take its toll on a survivor's mindset and consequentially, rumination over distressing experiences is likely. Sleep issues can lead to poor physical and mental health and exacerbate post-trauma symptoms.”¹⁴

Noll and Trickett write that, “Sleep disturbance is arguably a troubling factor for childhood trauma victims as this routine is associated with comfort and safety and once it has been interfered with during childhood, these associated feelings have been removed from the child's night-time regime. Children who have experienced physical and sexual abuse in the bedroom may struggle to fall asleep and maintain a full night of sleep because they have been personally violated in a typically secure setting. Mirroring this, research indicates that children who have experienced trauma, display signs of sleep disturbance almost instantly and report having nightmares as their most dominant post-trauma symptoms.”¹⁵ Thus, apart from the abused child and the teenager turning into a vitriolic bully who domineers over his compatriots and can become violent, the Bully himself or herself might suffer from mental maladies such as depression, anxiety and sleep disturbances.

Why Teenagers turn into Bullies and Criminals?

Discussions:

There are myriad reasons why adolescents and teenagers turn into bullies and subsequently into child delinquents along with being anti-social in their general behaviour through families, schools and colleges and even workplaces later on.

¹³ K. Butler, K. Klaus, L. Edwards, K. Pennington Elevated cortisol awakening response associated with early life stress and impaired executive function in healthy adult males *Hormones and Behavior*, 95 (2017), pp. 13-21

¹⁴ G. Belleville, S. Guay, A. Marchand Persistence of sleep disturbances following cognitive-behavior therapy for posttraumatic stress disorder *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 70 (4) (2011), pp. 318-327

¹⁵ J.G. Noll, P.K. Trickett, E.J. Susman, F.W. Putnam Sleep disturbances and childhood sexual abuse *Journal of Pediatric Psychology*, 31 (5) (2006), pp. 469-480

National Research Council and Institute of Medicine depicts in its reportage that, “A large number of individual factors and characteristics has been associated with the development of juvenile delinquency. These individual factors include age, gender, complications during pregnancy and delivery, impulsivity, aggressiveness, and substance use. Some factors operate before birth (prenatal) or close to, during, and shortly after birth (perinatal); some can be identified in early childhood; and other factors may not be evident until late childhood or during adolescence. To fully appreciate the development of these individual characteristics and their relations to delinquency, one needs to study the development of the individual in interaction with the environment. In order to simplify presentation of the research, however, this section deals only with individual factors.”¹⁶

Farrington writes that, “Studies of criminal activity by age consistently find that rates of offending begin to rise in preadolescence or early adolescence, reach a peak in late adolescence, and fall through young adulthood. Some lawbreaking experience at some time during adolescence is nearly universal in American children, although much of this behavior is reasonably mild and temporary. Although the exact age of onset, peak, and age of desistance varies by offense, the general pattern has been remarkably consistent over time, in different countries, and for official and self-reported data. For example, Farrington in a longitudinal study of a sample of boys in London (the Cambridge Longitudinal Study), “found an eightfold increase in the number of different boys convicted of delinquent behaviour from age 10 to age 17, followed by a decrease to a quarter of the maximum level by age 24.”¹⁷ Thus, it can be gleaned from the abovementioned argument that child delinquency is a social menace and a tangible challenge present before both the law enforcers and Medical professionals as when gun running for example happens in a school then the perpetrators being the young teenagers of school going age, the law makers too have to be different and innovative in their approach to either reform them or to bring them to justice and make them quit their anti-social ways due to a slew of sociological and psychological reasons.

The Psychology of a Bully: Discussions

Peter K Smith pens in his seminal work that, “Bullying is an evocative term. Most people will have witnessed it or experienced it in one form or another. But only since the 1980s has there

¹⁶ “The Development of Delinquency.” National Research Council and Institute of Medicine. 2001. *Juvenile Crime, Juvenile Justice*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. doi: 10.17226/9747

¹⁷ Rolf Noeber, David P Farrington, “Child Delinquents: Development Intervention and Service Needs,,” Penguin, 2012

been serious interest, both from researchers and from the wider community. Much of this was sparked by tragic events such as suicides due to being bullied at school, publicized by the media. WE can argue that what we mean by bullying. The history behind the study of it, and the main forms it takes, including the development of cyberbullying this century. The book as a whole is about bullying at school, or among school-aged pupils. But of course bullying can happen at college, at home, in the workplace and in other institutions. But for many people, bullying conjures up images of childhood, and of suffering which can be difficult to redress.”¹⁸ The fact that can be highlighted over here is that “Bullying” can be ranged with attendant and more commonly known and universally accepted human rights abuses. It’s here in that one can fathom and postulate that after the 1980’s the theme and the societal challenge of bullying became prominent area of research enquiry in the American academia. A ward has the indelible right to have education sans all freedom from fear, threat, persuasion, ragging and intimidation. Ragging in Schools and colleges is tantamount to bullying where in senior students who have failed and done shabbily in their courses tend to be the biggest bullies and vent out their social frustration at the fresher’s/ the new entrants in schools and Colleges.

It can be elaborated upon that, “The second example comes from a book by Diana and Victoria Webster, called *So many Everest’s*, published in 2010. Victoria Webster has cerebral palsy, and in this book, co-written with her mother Diana, her mother describes how she was bullied at school. For example “A smaller boy following her began to mimic her slight camel-like kick with one foot as she walked and another boy with him laughed and giggled” and Her schoolmates used to play what they called *Victoria-in-the Cage*. The game was for her classmates to put her in the middle and circle her with their desks. Gradually they pushed the desks closer and closer together and moved forwards, so that eventually she was forced to crawl under them to escape while they laughed and jeered at her.”¹⁹ Delving inside this incident, the experience can become more tormenting and horrendous if higher levels of delinquent matters are deliberated upon. All in all, the mimicry of the person and then the conjoined mockery and jeering of the girl child can be torment personified for a gentle and easy going should who is new to a place and its environment and its residents, whether it be a school, college or a neighbourhood.

¹⁸ Peter K Smith, “The Psychology of School Bullying,” Routledge: New York, 2019 Page no 10-15

¹⁹ Ibid

Peter K Smith further writes that, “In the US, there had been a lot of work on peer aggression in the 1980s and 1990s, but it was the Columbine High School massacre in 1999, in which two students shot and killed 12 other students and a teacher, that led to an increase in concerns about bullying. The two student shooters had reportedly been bullied previously, and a 2000 report found that many premeditated school shootings could be linked to bullying. Although coming in somewhat later than What is bullying in school and how has it been studied?.” He further mentions that, “Researchers in many other countries, bullying is now a major research topic in the US, and it is the single largest contributing country in terms of research output. Through the twenty-first century, school bullying has been picked up as an issue across the globe. There has been considerable work in South Korea, Hong Kong and Mainland China, Singapore and some other South-East Asian countries, and growing interest in South Africa and some other African countries, Arabic countries, South America, Russia and the Indian sub-continent.”²⁰ Thus, rankling and painful civil societal and sociological concerns, such as, bullying in schools were normally and ordinarily relegated to the backburner which is no more the reality today. As in the context of United States of America, the people have realised the menace of gun running which can be clubbed together as a kind of social security challenge which US faces in the context of gun running by delinquents ranging from Columbine to Georgia recently.

Results:

The paper attempts has arrived at a hypothesis that Bullying during the childhood years is a deviant behaviour which owes its origins to societal and familial upbringing along with harking back to a history of neurotic and psychological factors which vitiate the growth and development of the participant. The paper finds out that bullying and rash and domineering social behaviour is a common theme which now populates academic studies and narratives in psychological Studies.

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²⁰ Ibid 1
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